

Introducing Early-Stage Informatics Education in Primary Teacher Education

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Abstract. This paper presents an introductory module on informatics education, developed and implemented within a seminar on early-stage mathematics education for prospective primary school teachers. Building on the CS Unplugged approach, the module conveyed selected informatics concepts through hands-on, activity-based learning experiences. To assess its relevance for teacher education, the participating prospective primary school teachers completed a questionnaire exploring their perspectives on introductory informatics instruction in the context of first and second grade. The results indicate strong interest in the topic and highlight a clear demand for the broader and compulsory integration of informatics into teacher education curricula, as well as for its systematic implementation in primary schools.

Keywords: Informatics Education · Primary Teacher Education · CS Unplugged · Early-Stage Education

1 Introduction

The increasing integration of informatics concepts and current technological developments into all areas of life is fundamentally reshaping both the visible and invisible aspects of everyday experience. This ongoing transformation is expected to become one of the most powerful and far-reaching technological forces influencing how we live, work, and learn [16,7]. In response to these changes, fostering digital literacy requires individuals to develop a solid foundation in informatics-related competencies [7], which are essential not only for understanding how digital technologies function but also for engaging with them in a reflective and informed manner. In the context of teacher education, this is particularly important: prospective school teachers should be equipped to critically reflect on the implications of digital transformation and its underlying technologies. As professional development increasingly requires a basic understanding of how informatics concepts relate to educational contexts and societal change, it is essential to embed elements of foundational informatics education as part of academic qualification programs in contemporary primary and secondary teacher education [7,17]. While a compulsory informatics curriculum has now been introduced in many German federal states, it remains largely limited to secondary

schools [7]. In contrast, a dedicated informatics subject is currently not planned for primary schools [10]. Nevertheless, the upcoming core curriculum for mathematics in primary education in Lower Saxony, the federal state in which our university and its teacher education programs are located, is expected to incorporate elements of “*basic informatics education*” [13]. In light of these developments, it is becoming increasingly important to explore how prospective primary school teachers can be meaningfully prepared to integrate “basic informatics education” into the early years of schooling.

Preparing prospective primary school teachers for this challenge requires well-designed learning opportunities that are tailored to their specific needs and that foster active engagement in the learning process. Whether they benefit from such opportunities depends not only on the structure of the program but also on how they *perceive* the relevance and applicability of the subject matter. Their views, prior experiences, and confidence in teaching are likely to influence how they engage with the content and whether they consider it meaningful and realistic for their future professional development and classroom practice [18].

To contribute to this discourse, the present paper introduces a teaching module developed and implemented within a mathematics education course for prospective primary school teachers. In this context, our aim was twofold: First, the module was designed to provide an initial insight into how to prepare and develop teachers to introduce informatics competencies into the classroom, thereby supporting the development of the competencies required to address informatics as a future element of the primary mathematics curriculum [13]. Second, we sought to explore how prospective primary school teachers perceive the overall role of selected informatics concepts at the early stage of primary education. We describe the conceptual framework that guided the course design, outline the intended learning outcomes, and examine how the participants engaged with the module and perceived its relevance and applicability. Particular focus is placed on the *early stages* of instruction in grades 1 and 2, a domain that has so far received limited attention despite its growing importance, as research on informatics education at the primary level has largely concentrated on grades 3 and 4 (e.g., [6]). In this context, our evaluation of the workshop design is guided by the following research question (RQ):

RQ How do prospective primary school teachers perceive the potential, challenges, and overall role of early-stage informatics education in grades 1 and 2?

2 Early-Stage Education in Primary Schools

Introducing formal education in the early years of primary school plays a crucial role in establishing the foundation for essential learning processes and core competencies [3]. While educational systems differ in how they structure and conceptualize the first years of schooling, there is broad consensus that even young learners are capable of meaningfully engaging with fundamental ideas across

subject areas. This perspective reflects Bruner’s well-known principle that “any subject can be taught to anybody at any stage in some form that is honest.”¹

Such instruction typically begins with simplified core ideas that are developmentally appropriate and is progressively expanded and deepened as learners advance. This recursive structure strengthens long-term retention by continuously linking new knowledge to previously established foundations. It reflects a pedagogical stance that emphasizes conceptually rich and age-appropriate learning experiences from the very beginning of formal education [3].

Instruction during the initial years of primary school should be intuitive, meaningful, and embedded in concrete, relatable contexts. It should provide learners with accessible entry points into subject-specific thinking and problem-solving. In the German educational framework, the first two years of primary school are referred to as the phase of “*Anfangsunterricht*”, a notion we describe in this paper as *early-stage education*. This foundational period is characterized by playful exploration, experiential learning, and holistic development, deliberately avoiding abstract formalism and excessive technical complexity (e.g., [20]).

2.1 Content Selection

Our approach to early-stage informatics education, including the corresponding preparation of prospective primary school teachers, is primarily guided by the Educational Recommendations in Informatics for Primary Education [10], with a particular focus on the competencies that pupils are expected to acquire by the *end of grade 2*. The underlying model (see Fig. 1) is conceived as an integrated framework in which various content and process domains are closely interrelated to form a coherent educational approach [10].

Based on these foundations, the author team systematically reviewed and discussed a range of established CS Unplugged activities suitable for early-stage education. The final selection included binary numbers, image compression, error detection, sorting networks, and finite-state automata [2,19], each corresponding to one or more of the core competencies outlined in the model. Particular emphasis was placed on the content domain “Informatics, Humans, and Society”, which was not treated as a separate topic but deliberately embedded across all activities in an integrative manner. This purposeful integration aimed to promote meaningful connections between informatics concepts and learners’ everyday experiences, thereby highlighting the societal relevance of informatics from the very beginning of primary education (see Sec. 3 for further details).

Since the selected activities (e.g., [2]) are pre-existing and well-researched, their targeted use within an early-stage education seminar for prospective primary school teachers – including specific adaptations such as an integrative focus, the structured inclusion of Bebras tasks, and guided reflection (see Tab. 1) – allowed us to purposefully combine and align these elements to meet our goals for early-stage informatics education (see Sec. 1).

¹ This principle forms the foundation of Bruner’s concept of the *spiral curriculum* [3], a pedagogical approach in which learners revisit essential topics repeatedly, each time at a higher level of abstraction and complexity.

(a) Content and process domains of the GI recommendations for informatics education [10].

(b) Excerpt of content-related competencies [10].

Fig. 1: Content Selection for Early-Stage Informatics Education

2.2 Approaches to Teaching Early-Stage Informatics

A variety of strategies have been proposed for teaching informatics in the context of early-stage education (e.g., [20,5]). The following examples illustrate some of the approaches discussed in the literature:

- **Unplugged computing**, such as CS Unplugged, conveys core informatics concepts through physical and embodied activities without the use of computers [2,14].
- **Plugged computing** (screen-based approaches), including block-based programming tools such as Scratch, supports the development of algorithmic thinking through visual representations [11,15].
- **Tangible computing** involves manipulatives and enactive programming environments to make computational structures physically graspable [9].

A mixed-strategy approach is frequently recommended, beginning with unplugged activities and gradually integrating digital tools to support the transition to plugged computing [15]. This combination helps learners engage with abstract concepts through active involvement and concrete experiences, thereby fostering deeper understanding. A valuable complement to this approach is the integration of the *Bebras Computing Challenge* [1]. Its short and engaging tasks, designed for learners as young as five, have proven particularly effective in promoting algorithmic thinking, problem-solving, and abstraction in an accessible and motivating way [1,21].

3 Workshop Concept

To address the current lack of informatics education in primary schools, we developed and implemented a workshop on early-stage informatics, which was

integrated into a mathematics education seminar for prospective primary school teachers (see Tab. 1).

Scope	Focus	Format
•	Introduction to early-stage informatics and context	Presentation
•••	CS Unplugged: A1 – Binary numbers	Participation
•	Bebras task (related)	Participation
••	Discussion: relevance and learning goals	Reflection
•••	CS Unplugged: A2 – Image representation	Participation
•	Bebras task (related)	Participation
••	Discussion: relevance and learning goals	Reflection
•••	CS Unplugged: A3 – Error detection	Participation
•	Bebras task (related)	Participation
••	Discussion: relevance and learning goals	Reflection
•••	CS Unplugged: A4 – Sorting networks	Participation
•	Bebras task (related)	Participation
••	Discussion: relevance and learning goals	Reflection
•••	CS Unplugged: A5 – Finite-state automata	Participation
•	Bebras task (related)	Participation
••	Discussion: relevance and learning goals	Reflection
•	Summary and outlook on various early-stage approaches	Closure

Legend: • = brief •• = moderate ••• = extended

Table 1: Structure of the Workshop

The workshop (approx. 120 minutes) on early-stage informatics education was conducted during the eleventh session of a fourteen-part seminar series focused on early-stage mathematics education. By this point in the course, participants had already engaged with key didactic principles of early-stage education (see Sec. 2). All students were enrolled in a master’s program preparing them to teach at the primary level, with mathematics as one of their two major subjects. While most had prior experience with digital tools in mathematics education, their exposure to informatics-specific content was limited. In light of this, the workshop was deliberately designed as a low-threshold introduction to informatics, requiring no prior knowledge in the field. Given the limited time frame, the session focused exclusively on *CS Unplugged activities* [2], which made it possible to address selected key informatics concepts (see Sec.2.1) in a hands-on and age-appropriate way. As outlined in Section 2.2, early informatics education can involve unplugged, plugged, or tangible formats; however, combining all three within the available time would not have been feasible. CS Unplugged was therefore chosen for its accessibility, enabling immediate engagement without technical infrastructure or prior experience with digital tools. This focus also allowed for a stronger emphasis on conceptual understanding and guided reflection within the given constraints.

The workshop concentrated on five informatics concepts (see Sec. 2.1): the representation of information (A1 binary numbers, A2 image compression, A3 error detection), algorithmic thinking (A4 sorting networks), and system modeling (A5 finite-state automata). Each concept was introduced through a consistent

instructional sequence (see Tab. 1), beginning with a CS Unplugged activity [2], followed by a related Bebras Computational Thinking task (see Sec. 2.2) designed to reinforce the underlying concepts in a motivating and age-appropriate way (*participation*), and concluding with a guided *reflection*. The session opened with a brief introduction outlining its goals and structure (*presentation*). In line with the principles of discovery learning [8], direct instruction was deliberately minimized to promote active exploration: Each CS Unplugged activity was briefly introduced at the beginning of the respective session, after which the students carried out the tasks independently based on a visual and written task description provided by us (see Fig. 2). By taking on the role of primary school learners, they engaged with the activities from a learner’s perspective, which in turn provided the foundation for subsequent didactic analysis and reflection [2].

CS Unplugged Activity: Sorting Network

Instructions:

1. Form groups of six students. Each student takes one numbered card.
2. Line up at the left side of the field, at the starting points labeled "START". Your numbers should be in random order.
3. Follow the paths (lines) that lead you to comparison points (the circles). When you arrive at a circle, wait until another team member arrives.
4. Compare your numbers with each other:
The person with the smaller number takes the left path; The person with the larger number takes the right path.
5. Continue following the marked paths until you reach the end of the field.

Check your result:
Are you in the correct ascending order when you reach the right side of the field?
If not, your team has made a mistake. Start over and make sure you've applied the rule at every comparison point:
Smaller number → left path, larger number → right path.

Fig. 2: Excerpt from Activity A4 (*Participation*), adapted from Bell [2].

The workshop concluded with a comparative discussion of unplugged, plugged, and tangible computing approaches to early-stage informatics instruction (*closure*, see Sec. 2.2), encouraging students to reflect on various modes of concept delivery and their relevance for classroom practice.

4 Evaluation and Discussion of the Workshop Results

To enable a holistic examination of the workshop in the context of early-stage informatics education in primary teacher education, the perspectives of participating prospective primary school teachers were collected following its implementation. A qualitative questionnaire ($n = 21$) served as the data collection instrument, and responses were gathered immediately after the participants had

completed the workshop. The data were analyzed using qualitative content analysis following Mayring’s approach [12], combining both deductive (based on our guiding questions) and inductive (based on the participants’ responses) category development. The analytical process was supported by MAXQDA 2024.

The coding procedure followed the approach proposed by Campbell et al. [4]: one rater identified relevant text passages, developed the category system, and applied it to the material, while a second rater independently applied the same system to a randomly selected subset of the completed questionnaires (approximately one third of the data). The results were compared, ambiguities were discussed, and the category system was refined. Once all discrepancies had been resolved, the entire dataset was (re)coded.

4.1 Perceived Benefits and Implementation Barriers

The results of the analysis offer valuable insights into the perceived *potentials* (see Tab. 2) and *challenges* (see Tab. 3) associated with implementing CS Unplugged in early-stage informatics education (see **RQ**).

Category	Definition	Anchor Example
K1: Development of cognitive and process-related competencies	Early-stage informatics education fosters core cognitive skills such as logical reasoning, algorithmic thinking, problem-solving strategies, systematic action, and process-related competencies, such as modeling and implementing.	“I consider informatics education in the second grade to be highly important, as it lays the foundation for technological competencies and fosters essential cognitive skills such as logical thinking, understanding process-related competencies, and creative problem-solving.” (w6)
K2: Real-life relevance and early digital literacy	Playful, everyday-oriented tasks enable children to develop a basic understanding of (digital) technologies and encourage early critical reflection (on media use). At the same time, such approaches help reduce (stereotypes and) barriers through the conveyed concepts of informatics, fostering early digital literacy and problem-solving skills.	“Children in the second grade already come into contact with various technological devices such as smartphones, tablets, laptops, etc., and sometimes use them in educational settings. I therefore consider a basic informatics education to be essential in order to understand these devices and applications and to use them appropriately and meaningfully in context — including the underlying principles and ideas behind the technology itself.” (m1)
K3: Fostering creativity, teamwork, and social skills	Many CS Unplugged tasks involve collaboration, communication, and creative thinking. These activities promote not only subject-specific knowledge, but also social competencies and a sense of participation and ownership.	“Teamwork and communication are strengthened through collaborative problem-solving.” (w1)
K4: Interdisciplinary learning and individual support	The activities offer connections to other subjects such as mathematics, arts, or science. They also provide differentiated learning opportunities for students with varying needs and abilities.	“The tasks not only promote an understanding of informatics but also support cross-curricular learning in subjects such as mathematics, technology, and more.” (m2)

Original quotes have been slightly edited for grammar and clarity.

Table 2: Perceived Potentials of Early-Stage Informatics Education

From the participants’ perspective, CS Unplugged emerged as a versatile and inclusive approach to introducing core informatics concepts at the primary level.

Four overarching categories (K1–K4) illustrate the perceived educational value of unplugged activities. First, participants emphasized their potential to foster cognitive and process-related competencies such as logical reasoning, algorithmic thinking, and problem-solving (K1), even in the absence of digital devices – both for young learners and for the student teachers themselves. This perspective aligns with existing research on the value of non-digital, embodied learning environments for developing computational thinking skills [2,19]. Second, the approach was praised for promoting digital literacy and real-life relevance from an early age (K2), while also reducing barriers and stereotypes through playful, everyday-oriented tasks. Third, participants highlighted the promotion of creativity, collaboration, and social skills (K3), supported by the interactive and game-based nature of the activities, which were considered especially suitable for young learners. Finally, the interdisciplinary potential of CS Unplugged (K4) was emphasized, particularly its applicability across various subjects and its accessibility for diverse learner groups.

Despite the overall positive perception of CS Unplugged, the analysis also revealed three overarching challenges: the cognitive demands of the content (K1), structural and organizational conditions in the classroom (K2), and teacher expertise and didactic integration (K3) (see Tab. 3).

Category	Definition	Anchor Example
K1: Abstract concepts and cognitive overload	Many informatics concepts such as algorithms, binary numbers or sorting processes are highly abstract and can be difficult for younger learners to grasp. Simplifying them to a suitable level for early-stage primary education is a major challenge. There is also a risk of cognitive overload due to complexity, dual number systems, or lack of prior knowledge.	“Informatics concepts such as algorithms, data structures or binary numbers are often very abstract and must be strongly simplified for children in primary school. The understanding of these concepts may not yet be fully developed at this age.” (m2)
K2: Instructional planning, time constraints and classroom management	The implementation of CS Unplugged activities demands careful planning and is often challenged by limited preparation time, tight lesson schedules, and heterogeneous learning speeds. Primary school teachers also mention space constraints and the challenge of managing student attention during active, movement-based tasks.	“The implementation of these active tasks, which involve a lot of movement, can cause loss of focus or lead to restlessness. They are also more time-consuming – both in preparation and in execution.” (w1)
K3: Teacher expertise and didactic integration	Many prospective primary school teachers lack confidence or training in informatics, which makes it difficult to explain CS Unplugged activities accurately and connect them to relevant concepts. Integrating such activities meaningfully into the mathematics curriculum remains a key challenge.	“I see challenges especially in the subject-specific classification of the activities in terms of their connection to informatics. Especially for teachers with limited expertise, the informatics part might feel too disconnected from the activities.” (m1)

Original quotes have been slightly edited for grammar and clarity.

Table 3: Perceived Challenges in Early-Stage Informatics Education

Participants emphasized the abstract nature of many informatics concepts, such as algorithms or binary numbers, which are often difficult to adapt appropri-

ately for younger learners. They also noted practical constraints, including limited instructional time, the effort required for planning and material preparation, and the challenge of managing group dynamics during interactive, activity-based formats. A frequently mentioned issue was the limited informatics expertise and didactic confidence of many primary school teachers. This lack of background knowledge can hinder their ability to explain core concepts clearly or to integrate informatics meaningfully into broader curricular structures under the formal umbrella of mathematics lessons [13]. As a result, participants expressed a need for targeted didactic support, sufficient preparation time, and accessible professional development opportunities. These findings suggest that while the goals of early-stage informatics education are widely supported and are soon to be anchored in the mathematics curriculum in this federal state [13], successful implementation depends on adequate structural and pedagogical conditions.

4.2 Dimensions of Teacher Perspective on Early-Stage Informatics Education

To gain insight into how prospective primary school teachers assess the implementation and overall relevance of early-stage informatics education in grades 1 and 2 (see **RQ**), the analysis was guided by the overarching question of how informatics can be meaningfully introduced in early primary education, with particular attention to practical feasibility, teacher confidence, and the role of initial teacher education. The following section summarizes the key themes that emerged from their responses.

Dimension 1: Perceived Feasibility and Structural Conditions. Most participants considered the implementation of early-stage informatics education in primary classrooms to be fundamentally feasible, especially when supported by low-threshold, device-free approaches such as CS Unplugged. These activities were perceived as age-appropriate and easy to integrate into existing classroom routines (m2, m6, w5). However, the lack of curricular anchoring was repeatedly identified as a critical barrier, with informatics often seen as an “add-on” (m2) or a “side topic” (m1), making it prone to being overlooked due to time constraints and overloaded curricula (m9, w4, w10). In addition to curricular challenges, participants pointed to a lack of teacher expertise, insufficient institutional support, and limited access to appropriate teaching materials as further obstacles to sustainable implementation. While some respondents acknowledged the potential for interdisciplinary connections to subjects such as mathematics or science (m2, m10, w8), others expressed concern that, without stronger political backing and clearer curricular integration, informatics content would remain marginalized or deprioritized in everyday teaching practice (m3, w4, w6, w7).

Dimension 2: Confidence in Teaching and Personal Engagement. Many prospective teachers initially reported limited exposure to informatics and expressed insecurities about teaching outside their subject specialization (m1, m8, w1, w4). Despite these concerns, most noted that participating in the workshop had

strengthened both their confidence and interest in the subject. This positive shift was largely attributed to the accessible and concrete nature of unplugged activities, which helped demystify informatics and made its core concepts more tangible (m2, m7, m10, w5, w6). Through engagement with practical, low-threshold examples, participants came to appreciate the pedagogical value of introducing early-stage informatics education without relying on digital tools (m2, w6, w9). This was particularly impactful for those who had previously associated informatics primarily with the use of technical equipment rather than with conceptual understanding (m9, w9). Nevertheless, a small number of respondents remained hesitant, citing persistent uncertainties about their content knowledge and concerns about meeting instructional expectations (m10, w4, w10). These participants emphasized the need for ongoing training opportunities and sustained professional support to build lasting confidence in teaching informatics.

Dimension 3: Role of Teacher Education and Professional Development. Across all responses, there was broad agreement that teacher education must play a central role in the successful integration of informatics at the primary level. Participants emphasized the need for dedicated modules on informatics within teacher education programs, either embedded in subjects such as mathematics or offered as standalone seminars (m1, m6, w1, w4, w5, w10). Practical learning formats such as workshops or teaching labs were considered particularly valuable for fostering both competence and sustained engagement (m7, w6, w9). At the same time, the importance of ongoing professional development was consistently emphasized, with a focus on hands-on teaching strategies, adaptable materials, and long-term institutional support (m4, w6, w8, w9). CS Unplugged was frequently mentioned in this regard as a promising gateway approach that can lower entry barriers and boost motivation, especially among educators with limited prior experience in informatics (m7, m10, w7). However, concerns were also raised about the feasibility of implementing such programs on a broader scale, particularly due to time constraints, limited financial resources, and staffing shortages (m3, w1). Despite these anticipated challenges, participants broadly agreed that targeted training opportunities and systemic support structures are essential for preparing a confident and competent teaching workforce capable of sustainably integrating informatics into primary education through the upcoming mathematics curriculum [13].

5 Conclusion

This paper examines how prospective primary school teachers perceive the potential, challenges, and overall role of introducing early-stage informatics education in grades 1 and 2. Embedded within a primary mathematics education seminar, a low-threshold unplugged approach enabled participants to engage in hands-on activities and reflect on the relevance, feasibility, and implementation of informatics content in early learning contexts. While many prospective primary school teachers reported increased confidence and a growing interest in

teaching informatics, they also expressed concerns about limited instructional time, insufficient training opportunities, and the persistent lack of curricular integration within teacher education. These challenges are closely tied to the broader context of primary teacher education in Germany, where informatics has traditionally been taught only at the secondary school level [17], resulting in a lack of established pathways for integrating it into primary education. Nevertheless, prospective mathematics teachers are increasingly recognizing the educational value of informatics – not only for children’s development but also for their *own* professional growth. The recent introduction of “basic informatics education” [13] as part of the primary mathematics curriculum marks an important turning point in this regard, offering a concrete step toward closing existing gaps and supporting a more systematic and sustainable integration of informatics into early-stage education.

The overall workshop experience motivates an extension of the concept: this project may form the basis for a dedicated seminar on early-stage informatics education for prospective primary school mathematics teachers, accompanied by further research building on the findings of this study. Future investigations will include more diverse samples and adopt longitudinal designs. Comparative studies between unplugged and plugged approaches may also help identify which methods are perceived as most effective by both student teachers and children across different instructional settings. Although the study was limited to a specific group of participants from the University of Hildesheim, the findings offer valuable insights into our underlying conceptual framework, as well as into the perceived potential, challenges, and overall role of early-stage informatics education from the perspective of the participating student teachers.

Finally, the findings emphasize that while the educational value and general feasibility of early-stage informatics education are widely acknowledged, its meaningful and sustainable integration requires coordinated curriculum development and comprehensive, systematic support structures across both initial teacher education and ongoing professional development. These include practice-oriented seminar formats, ready-to-use teaching materials, and institutional conditions that enable long-term implementation. Many additional steps need to be taken to determine effective ways of preparing and supporting teachers in introducing early-stage informatics education. This paper represents one of many steps forward.

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